

	Generalist		Specialist		Statistic	p-value
	Q2	IQR	Q2	IQR		
Unavailable niche	0.024	0.082	0.185	0.357	21.802	3.02e-06
Unoccupied niche	0.135	0.182	0.086	0.229	2.084	1.49e-01
Used niche	0.803	0.175	0.627	0.325	16.191	5.73e-05
Unavailable distribution	0.001	0.014	0.039	0.190	17.859	2.38e-05
Unoccupied distribution	0.011	0.033	0.020	0.046	0.014	9.04e-01
Used distribution	0.972	0.064	0.874	0.223	18.535	1.67e-05
Centroid Shift	0.066	0.092	0.142	0.188	20.681	5.43e-06
Environmental Relocation	0.010	0.014	0.025	0.047	17.704	2.58e-05
Niche Dissimilarity	0.838	0.099	0.726	0.146	37.816	7.77e-10
Niche Breadth difference	0.014	0.053	0.091	0.141	14.199	1.65e-04